

Appendix A

Table 1 Software metrics for CC1

Software Metric	Description
Resolved Tasks' Throughput	Density of tasks whose resolution didn't take longer than the defined duration threshold
Task-Type in a Timeframe	Density of tasks of particular type within a defined timeframe
Bug Identification Performance	Density of bugs identified before release date
Bug Correction Throughput	Density of bugs that were corrected within the defined duration threshold
Bug Leakage	Density of bugs identified after the release
Error Identification Performance	Density of errors identified in a given timeframe
Fast Tests	Density of tests that are under the testing duration threshold
Reopened Tickets	Density of tickets that have been reopened by testers
Developer-Tester Communication cycle	Density of developer-tester communication on a given issue
Timely feature specifications delivery	Density of feature specifications delivered internally on time during development cycle
Timely feature delivery	Density of features delivered internally on time during development cycle
Core component commits	Density of core component commits in a given period before the planned release
Non-issue component commits	Density of commits that not related to an identified issue in a given period (1 month) before the planned release
End User Feedback	Density of end user feedback related to an issue in a given period
Complexity	Density of files that do not exceed a defined average complexity per function
Postponed Issues Ratio	Ratio of non-critical issues which has not been closed
Development Task Completion	Density of project task which has been completed"
Quality Requirement Acceptance	Density of quality requirement not rejected by project manager
Quality Requirement Derivation	Density of accepted quality requirement derived as concrete mitigation tasks
Mitigation Task Completion	Density of mitigation action derived from quality requirement which has been completed
Duplication Density	Density of files lying within a defined range of duplication density"
Specification Task Completion	Density of specification task which has been completed
Comment Ratio	Density of files lying within a defined range of comment density
Passed Tests Percentage	Density of passed tests

Table 2 Software metrics for CC2

Software Metric	Description
Daily build performance	Density of daily builds with duration below the defined threshold
Automated Testing Performance	Density of automated tests with duration below the defined threshold
Commit Response Performance	Density of commits with duration below the defined threshold
Commit Review Performance	Density of commit reviews with duration below the defined threshold
Commit Review Iterations	Density of commits with number of iterations below the defined threshold
Error Correction Performance	Density of errors corrected with duration below the defined threshold
Error Identification Performance	Density of errors identified in a given timeframe
Old Issues	Density of issues of a given priority older than the defined creation threshold
Resolved Issues	Density of issues resolved in a timeframe
Resolved Issues' Throughput	Density of resolved issues with lifetime below the defined threshold
Team Throughput	Density of issues resolved in a given timeframe
Well-defined issues jira	Density of issues created within the last month that have required properties untouched"
Code complexity	Density of files that do not exceed a defined average complexity per function"
Comments ratio	Density of files lying within a defined range of comment density"
Duplication density	Density of files lying within a defined range of duplication density"
Non-blocking files	Density of files not having CRITICAL or BLOCKER issues"
Non-error density	Density of open issues not being errors"

Table 3 Software metrics for CC4

Software Metric	Description
Resolved issues throughput	Average time taken to resolve an issue
Bug density	Density of tickets of type 'non-bug' to total tickets on the board
Pending ticket density	Density of tickets that are pending testing
Estimated ticket density	Density of tickets of type 'estimated' to total tickets on the board that should be estimated
Spent density	Density of tickets that are pending testing
Non-blocking files	Density of files not having CRITICAL or BLOCKER issues"
Duplication density	Density of files lying within a defined range of duplication density"
Comments ratio	Density of files lying within a defined range of comment density"